

The categories of social pedagogy

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Annotation. This article discusses the categories of social and pedagogical activity. The process of socio-pedagogical activity is considered.

Аннотация. В данной статье будут рассмотрены категории социально-педагогической деятельности. Рассматривается процесс социально-педагогической деятельности.

Keywords: pedagogy, category, education, training, upbringing, activity and technology.

Ключевые слова: педагогика, категория, образование, обучение, воспитание, деятельность и технология.

Introduction

The main categories of social pedagogy are the most general and fundamental concepts reflecting its main components. These include: socio-pedagogical process, socio-pedagogical activity, social development, social education, social adaptation and maladaptation, socialization, social rehabilitation, socio-pedagogical correction, re-education, correction, etc. The essence of the categories is discussed in the relevant chapters of the manual.

The purpose (purpose) of social pedagogy is to promote the social formation of a personality, a group, taking into account its uniqueness and the socioculture of the state (society) in which it will live. Originality refers to what distinguishes one person (group) from another (other). It can manifest itself in age differences, volitional characteristics, and individual capabilities (for example, people with special needs, disabilities).

The subject of social pedagogy is a socio-pedagogical process that defines the principles, forms, methods of research of practical activity and conditions for its implementation. However, the above does not fully disclose the content of the subject of social pedagogy. Therefore, each section will complement it.

The content of social pedagogy is determined by its functions, each of which represents one of its directions reflecting its content. Functions (from Latin. *functio*

— departure, activity) — duty, scope of activity, purpose. The functions of social pedagogy help to understand its content. These include:

Cognitive — the study of the practice of pedagogical activity by its authorized representatives (social educators; persons performing socio-pedagogical activities) or specially trained people (researchers, graduate students, doctoral students).

Scientific — the study of the patterns of social development, socialization of a person, the influence of environmental factors on him, the development of a theoretical framework justifying socio-pedagogical phenomena.

Diagnostic (evaluative) is the diagnosis of social in a person, the social identity of a group, the implementation of a socio-pedagogical assessment (examination) of documents, the activities of institutions, individual specialists, as well as factors of society, processes occurring in it.

Prognostic — determining the prospects (immediate and long-term) for the development of socio-pedagogical processes of the environment, the manifestation of a person in it, his personality, as well as the possibilities of appropriate influence on them (the environment and the person).

Explanatory — a description of socio-pedagogical phenomena, the conditions of their existence and the possibilities of transformation.

Adaptation is an activity aimed at stimulating the adaptation of a person to the environment or the environment to a person, taking into account his individuality (originality).

Transformative — social pedagogy is designed to change pedagogical realities, pedagogical relations, the educational process, and its content.

Correctional is the directed activity of specialists in correcting the process of social development and upbringing of children and adolescents, the process of educational activity of parents, educators.

Rehabilitation is the directed activity of specialists in restoring individual human capabilities for development, education, and professional activity.

Mobilization is the directed activity of specialists to intensify the efforts of a person, a group for certain actions and deeds.

Preventive (protective and preventive) is the directed activity of specialists in the prevention and overcoming of various social deviations in the formed personality, group.

Educational — the study of the content, methodology and provision of training for the social sphere.

Managerial is the directed activity of specialists in managing the process of social formation of personality, socio-pedagogical phenomena in a team, group.

The following main categories of social pedagogy are distinguished: education, training, upbringing, pedagogical activity, pedagogical process, pedagogical interaction, pedagogical technology, pedagogical task. Education is the process and result of introducing a person to knowledge about the world, values, and experience accumulated by previous generations. Learning is a specially organized, controlled process of interaction between teachers and students aimed at mastering knowledge, skills, and abilities in accordance with the set goals. Education is the process of transferring social and historical experience by older generations to new generations in order to prepare them for life and work necessary to ensure the further development of society.

Pedagogical activity is a special type of socially useful activity of adults, consciously aimed at preparing the younger generation for independent activity in accordance with economic, political, moral and aesthetic goals.

The pedagogical process is a directed and organized interaction between adults and children, realizing the goals of education in the conditions of the pedagogical system. Any process is a sequential change of one state by another. In the pedagogical process, this change is the result of pedagogical interaction. That is why pedagogical interaction as mutual activity, cooperation between teachers and students in the process of their communication, which results in mutual changes in their behavior, activities and relationships, is an essential characteristic of the pedagogical process. Pedagogical interaction, which belongs to one of the key concepts of pedagogy, is at the same time considered as a scientific principle underlying education.

Pedagogical interaction is a process that occurs between a teacher and a pupil in the course of educational work and is aimed at developing the student's personality. The basis of pedagogical interaction is cooperation, which is present in all types of activities — cognitive, labor, creative, forming the beginning of the social life of mankind. Pedagogical interaction between people becomes when adults (teachers, parents) act as mentors.

Pedagogical technologies are a set of tools and methods for reproducing theoretically grounded learning and upbringing processes that allow for the successful implementation of set educational goals. A pedagogical task is considered as a certain situation correlated with the purpose of pedagogical activity and the conditions of its implementation. There are various types and types of tasks that, one way or another, are tasks of social management. The first type includes meaningful pedagogical tasks (SDGs) aimed at changing the student, transferring him from one state to another.. Pedagogical tasks of the second type — functional (FPZ) — These

tasks are arranged in the form of a clearly defined system, which should lead to the formation of set properties of students, i.e. to the solution of meaningful pedagogical tasks. Due to the fact that social pedagogy has become an independent science relatively recently, having separated from pedagogy, and the object of their study is almost the same, the division of categories belonging to different sciences will help to identify the specifics of social pedagogy. Many categories are taken by social pedagogy from pedagogy, but there are also their own, reflecting the specifics of its research. Concepts such as: education, upbringing - taken from pedagogy, personality. Philosophy has society, psychology has socialization, but there are also their own categories – social learning, social environment, social status, etc. The main concepts of social pedagogy are: social education, social training and socio – pedagogical activity, socialization.

Social pedagogy plays a huge role in the development of high-quality teachers. Social education is the education of an individual in society, social environment, social community in the course of his interaction with him. Social learning is learning that takes place in a broader environment than individual or group, in a social space, through social interaction between students. Such training may or may not lead to changes in behavior and attitudes. Socio-pedagogical activity is an activity aimed at the social protection of a child (teenager) and helping him to organize himself, his psychology. to establish normal relations in the family, at school, in society; to organize his education, rehabilitation and adaptation. Socialization is the process of assimilation and active reproduction of social experience by an individual, carried out in communication and activity.

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